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CRYSTAL PLASTICITY

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1. Introduction

The anisotropic elastoplastic deformation of crystalline aggregates including shape change, crystallographic texture, and strain hardening can be predicted by classical continuum crystal plasticity (Cailletaud et al., 2003; Roters et al., 2010). The most important aspect of crystalline plasticity is the dislocation glide or storage which acts as an obstacle to the material flow. It is possible to describe complex slip phenomena by including the silent micromechanical features in continuum description (Asaro, 1983). The main advantage of the Crystal Plasticity Finite Element Method (CPFEM) is its ability to solve mechanical problems under complicated internal and external boundary conditions (Roters et al., 2010). CPFEM also offers great flexibility to include various constitutive formulations for plastic flow and hardening for instance slip, twinning, and martensitic formulation. The CPFEM approach can be used at the micro and macroscopic scale. The experimental evidence of size effects can be found in different mechanical tests such as micro-torsion (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1997; Gao and Huang, 2001; Liu et al., 2012; Guo et al., 2017), micro-compression (Uchic et al., 2004; Greer et al., 2005), micro-bending (Stölken and Evans, 1998; Gao and Huang, 2001; Haque and Saif, 2003) and micro-indentation (Nix and Gao, 1998; Gao and Huang, 2001; Liu and Ngan, 2001) of crystalline materials.

The classical crystal plasticity formulation cannot predict the experimentally observed size effects such as precipitate or grain size effects and it does not involve any intrinsic material length scale (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1993, 1997). The size-dependent behaviour of a material can be predicted by introducing one or more intrinsic material length scale in the constitutive framework as in the strain gradient plasticity (SGP) approach. The SGP approach can be used to strain localization, softening and regularizing the numerical simulation of shear band formation in crystalline solids. Strain softening results in a narrow band of intense shearing i.e. gradual decrease of stress with increasing strain. The possible loss of ellipticity of partial differential equations in strain-softening materials results in an ill-posed boundary value problem and classically shows dependency on mesh size or density (Needleman, 1988). Without regularization, rate-independent models can not be used to solve shear band problems. Aifantis (Aifantis, 1984, 1987) added the gradient of plastic strain term in yield function of the conventional plasticity to solve the issues related to the thickness of the localization regime. Aifantis (1984, 1987); Zbib and Aifantis (1988); Chambon et al. (1998) linked the length scale in their model with the thickness and width of the shear band. The shear band dependency on the mesh size or density can be overcome by introducing intrinsic material length scale in conventional plasticity (Voyiadjis and Al-Rub, 2005; Anand et al., 2012; Peerlings et al., 2002; Vignjevic et al., 2018; Kaiser and Menzel, 2019).

It is possible to introduce the material length scale in the constitutive equation of the material microstructure by mechanics of generalized continua. The generalized continua can be classified into higher order and higher grade continua. The higher-order continua are based on the higher-order spatial derivative of the displacement field while higher grade continua introduce the additional degree of freedom so-called micromorphic approach (Eringen, 1999). The micromorphic approach used to investigate the strain localization phenomenon can be found in (Forest and Lorentz, 2004; Forest, 2005; Anand et al., 2012) and to predict size effect can be found in

(Aslan et al., 2011; Wulfinghoff et al., 2013; Ling et al., 2018; Scherer et al., 2019). The *microcurl* theory, which contains plastic microdeformation tensor as an additional degree of freedom in the sense of Eringen and Suhubi (1964) is proposed by Cordero et al. (2010) for small deformation and Aslan et al. (2011) for finite deformation. According to this theory, microdeformation tensor which is a counterpart of plastic part of the deformation gradient is introduced as an additional degree of freedom at each node. The penalty parameter is used to keep microdeformation close to plastic deformation. The microdeformation tensor enters the constitutive model as an argument of the energy density function and describe the kinematic-type hardening in cyclic non-uniform deformation (Ryś et al., 2020). The small deformation framework of micromorphic approach can be found in Forest (2009) and finite deformation framework in Forest (2016). The gradient of the scalar-valued internal variable is often used to regularise the formulation. A variant of *microcurl* model with scalar microstrain as an additional degree of freedom is proposed in Bayerschen et al. (2015); Bayerschen (2016). The SGP approach based on decomposition-coordination method, consists of duplicating the hardening variable. Among two, one instance of the variable is dedicated to nonlocality and other to nonlinearity (Zhang et al., 2018). The quasi-equality between microslip and micromorphic-like field variables is ensured by the Lagrange multiplier instead of the coupling modulus in micromorphic approach. This strong coupling scheme and rather a complex approach was shown to reduce the computational cost drastically.

The full gradient model which introduces the full dislocation density tensor in free energy density function gives more physical interpretation to phenomenological approaches (Kaiser and Menzel, 2019). The arising size effects are due to the back-stress component because of the action of higher-order stresses which is related to the presence of GNDs. A dislocation induced back-stress formulation in continuum description which includes the full tensorial nature of dislocation stress state can be found in (Bayley et al., 2006; Cordero et al., 2010; Kaiser and Menzel, 2019). The computational cost of SGP or micromorphic approach is rather high because it contains additional degrees of freedom. The computational cost can be drastically reduced by a reduced-order strain gradient crystal plasticity model proposed by (Wulfinghoff and Böhlke, 2012; Wulfinghoff et al., 2013; Erdle and Böhlke, 2017; Ling et al., 2018; Scherer et al., 2019) which contains only one additional degree of freedom.

The objective of the present deliverable is to give an overview of the crystal plasticity framework and its industrial context. The extension of classical continuum crystal plasticity to predict size effects called strain gradient crystal plasticity framework (reduced-order micromorphic and augmented Lagrangian SGP approach) is presented. The application of the strain gradient crystal plasticity is demonstrated by a numerical example of a microwire torsion test.

The outline of this deliverable is as follows. The industrial context of CPFEM is presented in section 2. The constitutive framework of continuum crystal plasticity and also rate-dependent and rate-independent formulations of crystal plasticity are presented in section 3. The size effects in plasticity, it's experimental evidence and numerical approach to quantify these size effects are presented in section 4. The reduced-order

micromorphic and it's a relaxed version called augmented Lagrangian SGP approach in presented section 5. The numerical example of microwire torsion test is presented in section 6. Concluding remarks follows in section 7.

The notations used in the deliverable are as follows. Underline $\underline{\mathbf{A}}$ and under-wave bold $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ are respectively for vectors and second-order tensors. The transpose, inverse, inverse of transpose and time derivative are represented as $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^T$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-1}$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-T}$ and $\dot{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}}$ respectively. The contraction product, outer product, dyadic product, and the tensorial product is written as $\underline{\mathbf{A}} : \underline{\mathbf{A}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{A}} \wedge \underline{\mathbf{A}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\underline{\mathbf{A}} \otimes \underline{\mathbf{A}}$ respectively.

2. Industrial context of CPFEM

The CPFEM can be used at a scale of micro as well as a macro. CPFEM is an important tool in micro-scale material testing where it is difficult to apply experimental boundary conditions rather difficult to control or monitor the material testing. In that case, it is difficult to interpret the experimental results and difficult to maintain the accuracy of the results. CPFEM simulations allow an experimentalist to simulate the effects in detail in contact and complicated boundary conditions. Nowadays, many products have a dimension of micron scale, for instance, micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) and many materials in electronic components. The design of such a micron scale part requires grain scale crystalline anisotropy (Roters et al., 2010). CPFEM applications at microscale includes indentation (Wang et al., 2004; Zaafarani et al., 2006; Casals et al., 2007), micro-compression (Raabe et al., 2007; Jung et al., 2015), micro-bending of thin foils (ming Zhang et al., 2013; Kuroda et al., 2006).

The macroscopic industrial application includes metal forming and texture simulation. These type of problems generally requires the homogenization models since this type of problems involves a large number of grains or phases. The primary application of CPFEM in metal forming includes the prediction of material shape after forming, material failure, material flow, thickness distribution for instance in sheet metal forming and in forging. Furthermore, the macroscopic applications are in press layout and tool design. CPFEM applications for deep drawing process can be found in (Nakamachi et al., 2001; Xie and Nakamachi, 2002), wire drawing (Očenášek et al., 2007; Delannay, 2018), extrusion (Li et al., 2008; Mayama et al., 2011), hydroforming (Zhuang et al., 2010; Weimin et al., 2011). The single crystal components in turbine blades and vane applications are subjected to high temperatures and stresses and the life prediction of these components becomes inaccurate. These issues can be addressed by CPFEM using the thermo-viscoplastic constitutive framework (Staroselsky and Cassenti, 2011). The advantage of CPFEM is that it is easy to compare the CPFEM predictions with the experimental prediction for instance shape change, strain, stresses, texture, and size effects.

In summary, the CPFEM can be used in complicated boundary conditions the materials which are difficult to test by experimental testing methods, various deformation mechanisms (e.g. slip, twinning and martensitic transformation) to predict the experimentally observed size effects, strain localization problems, structural superplasticity at a reasonable cost, for instance, using open source finite element codes.

Fig. 1: Material point deformation from reference to current configuration

3. Constitutive framework

3.1. Crystal Kinematics

It is based on the decomposition of the total deformation gradient ($\underline{\tilde{F}}$) multiplicatively into elastic ($\underline{\tilde{F}}^e$) and plastic parts ($\underline{\tilde{F}}^p$) as proposed by Lee and Liu (1967). The initial coordinates of the material points in the reference configuration are denoted by \underline{X} . The displacement vector $\underline{u} = \underline{x} - \underline{X}$, where \underline{x} is the coordinates of the material points in the deformed configuration. This material point is mapped by the total deformation gradient $\underline{\tilde{F}}$ which can be divided multiplicatively into the elastic part and plastic part ($\underline{\tilde{F}} = \underline{\tilde{F}}^e \underline{\tilde{F}}^p$). The elastic part is responsible for lattice rotation and distortion while the plastic part is responsible for the slip.

$$\underline{\tilde{F}}(\underline{X}) = \underline{\mathbb{1}} + \frac{\partial \underline{u}}{\partial \underline{X}} \quad (1)$$

The multiplicative decomposition leads to the following partition of the velocity gradient ($\underline{\tilde{L}}$) into elastic ($\underline{\tilde{L}}^e$) and plastic parts ($\underline{\tilde{L}}^p$).

$$\underline{\tilde{L}} = \underline{\tilde{L}}^e + \underline{\tilde{L}}^p, \quad \underline{\tilde{L}} = \dot{\underline{\tilde{F}}} \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^{-1} = \dot{\underline{\tilde{F}}}^e \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^{e-1} + \underline{\tilde{F}}^e \cdot \dot{\underline{\tilde{F}}}^p \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^{p-1} \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^{e-1} \quad (2)$$

The plastic deformation takes place through the slip of dislocations on prescribed lattice slip planes with normal \underline{n}^α along prescribed lattice slip direction \underline{m}^α :

$$\dot{\underline{\tilde{F}}}^p \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^{p-1} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \dot{\gamma}^\alpha (\underline{m}^\alpha \otimes \underline{n}^\alpha) \quad (3)$$

We introduce the Cauchy-Green (\underline{C}^e) and Green-Lagrange (\underline{E}^e) elastic strain measures:

$$\underline{C}^e = \underline{\tilde{F}}^{eT} \cdot \underline{\tilde{F}}^e \quad (4)$$

$$\underline{E}^e = \frac{1}{2} (\underline{C}^e - \underline{\mathbb{1}}) \quad (5)$$

The second Piola-Kirchoff's stress ($\boldsymbol{\pi}^e$) with respect to the isoclinic intermediate configuration is given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}^e = J^e \boldsymbol{F}^{e-1} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \boldsymbol{F}^{e-T} \quad (6)$$

where J^e is $\det \boldsymbol{F}^e$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. The plastic deformation process is constant volume process therefore $J^p = \det \boldsymbol{F}^p = 1$

3.2. Rate-dependent crystal plasticity model

The most rate-independent crystal plasticity theories lead to an ill-conditioned problem regarding the selection of active slip systems and the increments of shear on the active slip systems as emphasised in [Anand and Kothari \(1996\)](#); [Miehe et al. \(1999\)](#); [Busso and Cailletaud \(2005\)](#). One way to overcome this difficulty is to work with the rate-dependent framework. The phenomenological constitutive model mostly uses critical resolved stress as an internal variable. A rate-dependent flow rule is adopted to facilitate the determination of the active slip system. The shear strain rate ($\dot{\gamma}^r$) on each slip system (r) is given by Norton type flow rule

$$\dot{\gamma}^r = \dot{\gamma}_0 \left\langle \frac{|\tau^r| - \tau_c^r}{\tau_0} \right\rangle^n \text{sign}(\tau^r) \quad (7)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}_0$ and n are material parameters which control the rate sensitivity of the material response, a high value of n leads to low rate-sensitivity in a given strain-rate range. τ_0 is the initial critical resolved shear stress (CRSS), τ^r is the resolved shear stress (RSS) and τ_c^r is CRSS.

3.3. Rate-independent crystal plasticity model

Another way to select the active slip system is to work within the rate-independent formulation. In rate-independent formulation, a single yield function of all resolved shear stresses is used. The challenge which last-long with rate-independent plasticity is the smooth elastic-plastic transition. [Lubliner et al. \(1993\)](#) developed a rate-independent overstress model with a finite elastic range and a smooth elastic-plastic transition. The overstress model can be obtained by replacing plastic multiplier with the norm of the total distortion strain rate.

The rate-independent model proposed in [Forest and Rubin \(2016\)](#) characterized by a smooth elastic-plastic transition with no slip indeterminacy. The main idea is to replace Eq.(7) by following equation:

$$\dot{\gamma}^r = \dot{\epsilon}_{eq} \left\langle \frac{|\tau^r| - \tau_c^r}{R} \right\rangle^n \text{sign}(\tau^r) \quad (8)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}$ is a non-negative homogeneous function of degree one in the total velocity gradient \boldsymbol{L} . Here $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}$ is taken as total equivalent distortion strain rate:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \boldsymbol{D}' : \boldsymbol{D}'}, \quad \boldsymbol{D}' = \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{L} + \boldsymbol{L}^T) - \frac{1}{3}(\text{trace } \boldsymbol{L})\mathbf{1} \quad (9)$$

R is a positive constant having the unit of stress and which controls the amplitude of the rate-independent overstress.

4. Size effects in plasticity

The classical crystal plasticity incorporates the internal variable related to statistically stored dislocations (SSDs) to describe hardening behaviour. In classical crystal plasticity the contribution of SSDs density (ρ_S) to strain hardening is considered very high as compared geometrically necessary dislocations (GNDs) density, (ρ_G) i.e. ($\rho_S > \rho_G$). The gradient of shear strain results in the storage of GNDs. (Ashby, 1970; Acharya and Bassani, 2000; Gurtin, 2002; Cordero et al., 2012). The GNDs density controls the material strain hardening along with SSDs. The classical crystal plasticity formulation cannot predict the experimentally observed size effects wherein smaller is the size higher is the response. For example, the indentation hardness of metals and ceramics increases with decreasing the size of the indenter (Nix and Gao, 1998; Gao and Huang, 2001; Liu and Ngan, 2001). Micro-torsion test shows increasing shear strength with decreasing diameter of the microwire (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1997; Gao and Huang, 2001; Liu et al., 2012; Guo et al., 2017). The Micro-bending test shows an increase of material strength with a decrease in thickness of the beam (Stölken and Evans, 1998; Gao and Huang, 2001; Haque and Saif, 2003).

4.1. Experimental evidence of size effects

The most important aspect of the SGP is the precise determination of the intrinsic material length scale. When the length scale associated with the deformation field is large, strain gradients are small, and conventional crystal plasticity is sufficient. But when the length scale associated with the deformation field is small, strain gradients are large and we need to consider SGP. Several attempts have been made to investigate experimental evidence of intrinsic material length scale and it's a correlation with material microstructure (Nix and Gao, 1998; Fleck et al., 1994; Stölken and Evans, 1998). The micro-torsion (Fleck et al., 1994) and micro-bending (Stölken and Evans, 1998) tests have been conducted to estimate the material length and estimated value for nickel is $5 \mu\text{m}$ while $4 \mu\text{m}$ for copper. Qian et al. (2013) calibrated the temperature-dependent material length scale using indentation tests and the calibrated material length scale is further used for the FE simulations based on SGP. The micro and nano-indentation test carried out by (Abu Al-Rub and Voyiadjis, 2004; Voyiadjis and Al-Rub, 2005) found that the length scale is proportional to the mean free path of dislocations.

4.2. Numerical approach - Strain gradient plasticity

There are various SGP models introduced by many researchers to include the experimentally observed size effects. Aifantis (Aifantis, 1984, 1987) developed gradient plasticity theory with single material length scale based on Toupin-Mindlin (Toupin, 1962; Mindlin, 1964) elasticity theory. Aifantis added the plastic strain gradient term in the conventional yield function to combine intrinsic material length scale with conventional

Fig. 2: (a) Plot of experimental results of polycrystalline copper microwire torsion test for different diameters showing size effects, here $\frac{Q}{a^3}$ is the normalised torque, a is the radius of microwire, κ is the twist angle per unit length (Fleck et al., 1994) (b) Plots of normalized torque-twist curves for copper wires with diameter in the range 18–105 μm Liu et al. (2012)

Fig. 3: Plot of experimental results of bending test for different thickness of Nickel foil showing size effects (Stölken and Evans, 1998)

plasticity theory. Fleck and Hutchinson (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1993) developed a higher-order deformation theory of SGP which is generalized by Fleck and Hutchinson (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1997) and investigate the effect of void radius on normalised void growth rate on microscale voids. Niordson (Niordson, 2008) utilised the Fleck and Hutchinson (Fleck and Hutchinson, 2001) strain gradient theory with its extension to finite strain to study size effects on void growth and coalescence. Shu and Fleck (Shu and Fleck, 1999) investigated the influence of grain boundaries on the deformation of bicrystal using rate-dependent crystal plasticity formulation based on Fleck and Hutchinson (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1997) SGP. The strain gradient theory which involves the three independent length scale parameters is developed by Fleck and Hutchinson (Fleck and Hutchinson, 1997). Gao et al. (1999) and Huang et al. (2000) developed a mechanism-based SGP in which Taylor’s expression for hardening in terms of dislocation density is used and investigated the size effects in bending of thin beams, torsion of wires and micro-void growth. Cosserat model with an additional degree of freedom for rotation and their gradient to predict their effect on strain hardening can be found in (Forest and Sedláček, 2000). Gurtin and Anand (Gurtin and Anand, 2005a,b) developed a strain gradient theory for small deformation in the absence of plastic rotations based on the displacement gradient and based on the deformation gradient for finite strain deformation. The strain gradient model based on the curl of the displacement gradient ($\text{curl} \mathbf{H}^p$), which is a quantification of GNDs and subsequently takes account into the extra hardening due to strain gradients to predict the size effects is used by (Cordero et al., 2010). The implicit gradient plasticity theory proposed by (Peerlings et al., 1996) introduces a non-local variable ($\bar{\epsilon}^p$) and it’s gradient takes into account the extra hardening due to strain gradient instead of a gradient of equivalent plastic strain (ϵ^p). It allows to include the intrinsic material length scale implicitly in the constitutive model. In micromorphic continua, a microscopic variable is introduced in the conventional constitutive model by (Mindlin, 1964; Eringen and Suhubi, 1964). The elastoplastic micromorphic theory employed to investigate the strain localization in aluminum foam by Forest and Lorentz (2004) and Forest (2005). The approach shown to be able to regularize shear band formation. The thermodynamically consistent formulation of micromorphic gradient theory can be found in (Forest, 2009). The reduced-order micromorphic gradient theory which contains only one additional scalar variable as a degree of freedom is explained in next section.

5. A reduced-order strain gradient crystal plasticity theory

5.1. Micromorphic strain gradient crystal plasticity approach

The variables which suppose to carry targeted strain gradient effects are selected from the available state variable which can be tensor of any rank (Forest, 2009). Numerical implementation of reduced-order micromorphic gradient theory can be found in Ling et al. (2018). Here, we consider the scalar variable. Two types of degree of freedom (DOF) are applied to the material point, displacement vector ($\underline{\mathbf{u}}$), and scalar variable

microslip (γ_χ). Then the DOF at each node is 3 displacement and 1 microslip variable. The set of DOF is

$$\text{DOF} = \{\underline{\mathbf{u}}, \gamma_\chi\} \quad (10)$$

The gradient of the degree of freedom concerning reference configuration is given by

$$\underline{\mathbf{H}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}} = \text{Grad } \underline{\mathbf{u}}, \quad \underline{\mathbf{K}} = \frac{\partial \gamma_\chi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}} = \text{Grad } \gamma_\chi \quad (11)$$

The gradient of microslip variable concerning the current configuration is given by

$$\underline{\mathbf{k}} = \frac{\partial \gamma_\chi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{x}}} = \text{grad } \gamma_\chi = \underline{\mathbf{K}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} = \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{K}} \quad (12)$$

The volume mass density with respect to reference configuration (ρ_0), intermediate configuration ($\rho_\#$) and w.r.t. current configuration (ρ) given by the relation

$$J = \det \underline{\mathbf{F}} = \frac{\rho_0}{\rho} \quad J_e = \det \underline{\mathbf{F}}^e = \frac{\rho_\#}{\rho} \quad J_p = \det \underline{\mathbf{F}}^p = \frac{\rho_0}{\rho_\#} \quad (13)$$

5.1.1. Principle of virtual power

The principle of virtual power is used to formulate balance equations for the generalised micromorphic media. The virtual motion of sub-domain D of the body \mathbf{B} is given by the virtual velocity, $\nu = \{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}}, \dot{\gamma}_\chi\}$. The power of virtual internal forces comprises three parts, which are associated with velocity gradient, rate of microslip variable, and its gradient.

The virtual power of internal forces is given by

$$p^i = \int_D p^i dv = \int_D (\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \text{grad } \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + s \dot{\gamma}_\chi + \underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \text{grad } \dot{\gamma}_\chi) dV, \quad \forall D \subset \mathbf{B} \quad (14)$$

where $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is the Cauchy stress, s is the generalised stress work-conjugate to the rate of microslip variable, and vector stress $\underline{\mathbf{m}}$ is work conjugate to the rate of a gradient of microslip variable.

The virtual power of external forces comprises of two parts surface traction $\underline{\mathbf{t}}$ related to macroscopic motion and generalised surface traction m related to microslip

$$p^e = \int_{\partial D} p^e dS = \int_{\partial D} (\underline{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + m \dot{\gamma}_\chi) dS, \quad \forall D \subset \mathbf{B} \quad (15)$$

Then from Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) principal of virtual power can be written as

$$\int_D (\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \text{grad } \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + s \dot{\gamma}_\chi + \underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \text{grad } \dot{\gamma}_\chi) dV = \int_{\partial D} (\underline{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + m \dot{\gamma}_\chi) dS, \quad \forall \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}}, \forall \dot{\gamma}_\chi, \forall D \quad (16)$$

5.1.2. Balance laws

The balance equations and Neumann boundary conditions expressed w.r.t. current configuration are

$$\operatorname{div} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \operatorname{div} \underline{\boldsymbol{m}} - s = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{t}} = \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{n}} \quad \text{and} \quad m = \underline{\boldsymbol{m}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{n}} \quad (18)$$

where $\underline{\boldsymbol{n}}$ is normal to the surface.

The balance equations and Neumann boundary conditions expressed w.r.t. reference configuration are

$$\operatorname{Div} \underline{\boldsymbol{S}} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \operatorname{Div} \underline{\boldsymbol{M}} - S = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{T}} = \underline{\boldsymbol{S}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{n}}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad M = \underline{\boldsymbol{M}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{n}}_0 \quad (20)$$

where $\underline{\boldsymbol{S}}$ is the Boussinesq stress tensor, $\underline{\boldsymbol{S}}$, S and $\underline{\boldsymbol{M}}$ can be defined as

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{S}} = J \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \underline{\boldsymbol{F}}^{-T}, \quad S = Js, \quad \underline{\boldsymbol{M}} = J \underline{\boldsymbol{F}}^{-1} \underline{\boldsymbol{m}} \quad (21)$$

We consider a case in which the relation between cumulative plastic strain (γ_{cum}) and microslip variable (γ_χ) is given by relative plastic strain e .

$$e(\underline{\boldsymbol{X}}, t) = \gamma_{cum} - \gamma_\chi \quad (22)$$

The cumulative plastic strain γ_{cum} is introduced as

$$\gamma_{cum} = \int_0^t \sum_{r=1}^N |\dot{\gamma}^r| dt \quad (23)$$

5.1.3. Free energy potential

The material behaviour is characterised by the state variable space as

$$STATE = \{\underline{\boldsymbol{E}}_{GL}^e, e, \underline{\boldsymbol{K}}, \alpha\} \quad (24)$$

where α is the internal variable related to hardening, $\underline{\boldsymbol{E}}_{GL}^e$ is Green-Lagrange elastic strain tensor given as

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{E}}_{GL}^e = \frac{1}{2} (\underline{\boldsymbol{F}}^{eT} \underline{\boldsymbol{F}}^e - \underline{\mathbf{1}}) \quad (25)$$

The chosen free energy density function has quadratic potential form. The energy density function in reference configuration w.r.t. Green-Lagrange elastic strain tensor ($\underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e$), relative plastic strain (e), micromorphic plastic strain gradient ($\underline{\mathbf{K}}$), internal variable related to hardening (α) can be written as,

$$\rho_0 \Psi_0(\underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e, e, \underline{\mathbf{K}}, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2} J_p \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} : \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 H_\chi e^2 + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 \underline{\mathbf{K}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{K}} + \rho_0 \Psi_\alpha(\alpha) \quad (26)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ is the four order tensor of elastic moduli. In the micromorphic approach, two additional material parameters namely the coupling modulus H_χ and micromorphic stiffness $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ are used.

Which leads to Clausius-Duhem inequality as follows

$$\left(J_p \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^e - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e} \right) : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{E}}}_{GL}^e - \left(S + \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial e} \right) \dot{e} + \left(\underline{\mathbf{M}} - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{K}}} \right) \dot{\underline{\mathbf{K}}} + J_p \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^M : (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1}) - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \geq 0 \quad (27)$$

This provides the following state laws

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^e = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e} \quad S = -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial e} \quad \underline{\mathbf{M}} = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{K}}} \quad X = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \alpha} \quad (28)$$

From Eq. (27) obtained residual dissipation is as follows

$$D^{res} = J_p \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^M : (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1}) + S \dot{\gamma}_{cum} - X \dot{\alpha} \geq 0 \quad (29)$$

The thermodynamic forces associated with the state variables are given by

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^e = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} : \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e \quad (30)$$

$$S = -H_\chi e = -H_\chi (\gamma_{cum} - \gamma_\chi) \quad (31)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \underline{\mathbf{K}} \quad (32)$$

The dissipation inequality given in Eq. (29) can be further written as

$$D^{res} = J_p \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^M : \left(\sum_{r=1}^N \dot{\gamma}^r \underline{\mathbf{N}}^r \right) + S \dot{\gamma}_{cum} - X \dot{\alpha} \geq 0 \quad (33)$$

with resolved shear stress $\tau^r = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Pi}}}^M : \underline{\mathbf{N}}^r$, $\underline{\mathbf{N}}^r$ is Schmid tensor. X are the thermodynamic forces associated with internal variables (α) are

$$X^r = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi_0}{\partial \alpha^r} \quad (34)$$

The dissipation rate form gives an incentive to introduce following yield function

$$f^r = |\tau^r| + S - \tau_c^r = |\tau^r| - (\tau_c^r - S) \quad (35)$$

Finally, the rate-dependent flow rule is expressed as

$$\dot{\gamma}^r = \dot{\gamma}_0^r \left\langle \frac{|\tau^r| - \langle \tau_c^r - S \rangle}{\tau_0} \right\rangle^n \text{sign}(\tau^r) \quad (36)$$

The yield function using balance laws in Eq. (19) can be further simplified as

$$f^r = |\tau^r| - (\tau_c^r - S) = |\tau^r| - (\tau_c^r - \text{Div} \underline{\mathbf{M}}) \quad \text{and} \quad \underline{\mathbf{M}} = \underline{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{K}} \quad (37)$$

which gives an additional partial differential equation

$$\gamma_\chi - \frac{1}{H_\chi} \text{Div}(\underline{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{K}}) = \gamma_{cum} \quad (38)$$

For cubic symmetry crystal the second order tensor ($\underline{\mathbf{A}}$) is spherical which follows that $\underline{\mathbf{A}} = A \underline{\mathbf{1}}$ then above equation can be written as

$$\gamma_\chi - \frac{A}{H_\chi} \text{Div}(\underline{\mathbf{K}}) = \gamma_{cum} \quad (39)$$

As $\underline{\mathbf{K}} = \text{Grad} \gamma_\chi$, the above equation can be written as

$$\gamma_\chi - \frac{A}{H_\chi} \Delta_X \gamma_\chi = \gamma_{cum} \quad (40)$$

where Δ_X is Laplace operator w.r.t current configuration. Length scale (ℓ) which is an additional material parameter given by

$$\ell = \sqrt{\frac{A}{H_\chi}} \quad (41)$$

5.2. Augmented Lagrangian SGP model

The augmented Lagrangian SGP method is proposed by Fortin and Glowinski (1983) and successfully implemented in Zhang et al. (2018). The SGP approach based on augmented Lagrangian method consists of duplicating the hardening variable. Among two, one instance of the variable is dedicated to nonlocality and other to nonlinearity.

The chosen state variables set is

$$STATE = \{ \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e, e, \underline{\mathbf{K}}, \alpha, \lambda \} \quad (42)$$

where λ is an additional degree of freedom called Lagrange multiplier which enforces the quasi-equality between γ_{cum} and γ_χ .

The chosen Lagrangian energy density function (L_0) has quadratic form and can be given as

$$L_0(\underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e, e, \underline{\mathbf{K}}, \lambda, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2} J_p \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e : \underline{\mathbf{A}} : \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 H_\chi e^2 + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 \underline{\mathbf{K}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{A}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{K}} + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 \lambda (\gamma_{cum} - \gamma_\chi) + \rho_0 \Psi_\alpha(\alpha) \quad (43)$$

$$\left(J_p \underline{\Pi}^e - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e} \right) : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{E}}}_{GL}^e - \left(S + \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial e} \right) \dot{e} + \left(\underline{\mathbf{M}} - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{K}}} \right) \dot{\underline{\mathbf{K}}} + J_p \underline{\Pi}^M : (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1}) - \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \geq 0 \quad (44)$$

This gives the following state laws

$$\underline{\Pi}^e = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{E}}_{GL}^e} \quad S = -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial e} \quad \underline{\mathbf{M}} = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{K}}} \quad X = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \alpha} \quad (45)$$

From Eq. (44) residual dissipation is obtained as

$$D^{res} = J_p \underline{\Pi}^M : (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1}) + S \dot{\gamma}_{cum} - X \dot{\alpha} \geq 0 \quad (46)$$

The thermodynamic forces associated with the state variables are given by

$$\underline{\Pi}^e = \underline{\underline{\Lambda}} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{E}}}_{GL}^e \quad (47)$$

$$S = \lambda - \mu_\chi (\gamma_{cum} - \gamma_\chi) \quad (48)$$

where μ_χ is the penalty parameter

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}} \quad (49)$$

The dissipation rate form gives an incentive to introduce following yield function

$$f^r = |\tau^r| + S - \tau_c^r = |\tau^r| - (\tau_c^r - S) \quad (50)$$

$$f^r = |\tau^r| + S - \tau_c^r = |\tau^r| - (\tau_c^r - \lambda + \mu_\chi (\gamma_{cum} - \gamma_\chi)) \quad (51)$$

The penalty parameter μ_χ is similar to micromorphic penalization term H_χ but bears a completely different meaning. In reality, parameter μ_χ takes a much lower value than the H_χ and helps in providing additional coercivity.

5.3. Dislocation density-based hardening model

The strain hardening is based on dislocation density-based model. The hindrance to the dislocation motion is due to the interaction of the dislocations. The evolution of critical resolved shear stress τ_c^r based on scalar dislocation density is given (Kubin et al., 2008) as follows

$$\tau_c^r = \tau_0 + \mu \sqrt{\sum_{u=1}^N a^{ru} \rho^u} \quad (52)$$

where τ_0 is the initial critical resolved shear stress, μ is the shear modulus, a^{ru} is the interaction matrix describing long-range interaction between the dislocations and ρ^u is the scalar dislocation density. The evolution of dislocation density is given by the following equation

$$\dot{\rho}^r = |\dot{\gamma}^r| \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{u=1}^N b^{ru} \rho^u}}{k} - G_c \rho^r \right) \quad (53)$$

The first term in the above equation corresponds to dislocation generation and the second term corresponds to dislocation annihilation. b^{ru} matrix describes the dislocation interaction, k is the parameter proportional to the number of obstacles crossed by a dislocation before being immobilized, G_c is the critical distance controlling the annihilation of dislocations with opposite signs.

6. Numerical example - Size effects in microwire torsion

The torsion of single and polycrystal wires has been the subject of intensive experimental and computational research. Recently, the experimental microwire torsion test to study the size effects induced due to strain gradient has been carried out by [Liu et al. \(2012, 2013\)](#); [Gan et al. \(2014\)](#); [Guo et al. \(2017\)](#). [Nouailhas and Cailletaud \(1995\)](#) discovered that the torsion of a single crystal bar or tube is characterized by two types of strain gradients: a radial a gradient from the center to the outer surface due to the loading, but also a gradient along the outer circumference due to the anisotropic activation of slip systems. The size-dependent torsion of FCC single crystal microwires is investigated below using the proposed micromorphic and augmented Lagrangian SGP models.

6.1. Problem setup

Simulations are performed with a single crystal cylindrical microwire of diameter $D = 2R = 200 \mu m$ and $1000 \mu m$ height meshed with reduced integration 20 node brick elements (C3D20R). The various intrinsic length scale to diameter ratios ($\ell/2R$) considered in the simulations are given in the table 2. Cubic elasticity is considered. The bottom face of the microwire is clamped while the top surface undergoes a rigid body rotation around the wire axis. The lateral faces are kept traction free, which means that $\underline{T} = 0$ and $M = 0$ from Eq. (20). Two orientations of the single crystal are considered: $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ aligned with the microwire axis. The geometry and the boundary conditions are as shown the figure 4. The wrought Inconel 718 material parameters used for the numerical simulation are given in Table 1.

The Cartesian coordinate system is chosen for the two microwire single crystals $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ such that

$$X_1 = [001] \quad X_2 = [1\bar{1}0] \quad X_3 = [001]$$

and

$$X_1 = [\bar{1}\bar{1}2] \quad X_2 = [1\bar{1}0] \quad X_3 = [111]$$

respectively.

Fig. 4: microwire torsion (a) boundary conditions (b) example mesh from the top side in which black line represents the initial material line for $\langle 001 \rangle$ crystal orientation along $\langle 001 \rangle$ directions and for $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation along $\langle 11\bar{2} \rangle$ directions

Table 1: Numerical values of material parameters for the simulation of microwire torsion test

C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	τ_0	n	$\dot{\gamma}_0$	G_c	κ
259.6 GPa	179 GPa	109.6 GPa	320 MPa	20	10^{33} s^{-1}	10.4	42.8
r_0^s	a_1, \dots, a_6	$b_{ij} (i \neq j)$	b_{ii}	H_χ	μ_χ		
5.38×10^{-11}	0.124	1	0	10 000 MPa	1000 MPa		

6.2. Results and discussion

Fig. 5 and 6 show the accumulated plastic strain fields for FCC single crystals with wire axis parallel to $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ respectively for deformed configuration. A cross-section of each sample is illustrated in Fig. 5 and 6. The radial and circumferential plastic strain gradients are visible. A four-fold pattern is observed for the $\langle 001 \rangle$ specimen with maximum plastic strain values along $\langle 001 \rangle$ directions. A six-fold pattern is observed for the $\langle 111 \rangle$ specimen with maximum plastic strain values along $\langle 11\bar{2} \rangle$ directions. The overall curves are presented using conventional shear stress τ as a function of shear surface strain γ_R defined as

$$\tau = \frac{2\mathcal{M}}{\pi R^3} \quad \gamma_R = kR \quad (54)$$

where k is the applied twist per unit length (θ/L) and \mathcal{M} is the resulting torque. They are given in Fig. 7 for the two single crystal orientations $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ respectively using classical crystal plasticity. The $\langle 001 \rangle$ crystal orientation is found to be significantly stronger than the $\langle 111 \rangle$ wire. The orientation of the crystal to the loading direction causes different slip activity and results in different mechanical responses. The boundary effects at both ends of the microwire can be observed which causes the variation in the plastic strain field from the ends to the middle portion of the microwire. The warping of the cross-section is observed with increasing surface strain. The twist angle at the cross-section of the microwire is calculated as $\theta_H = \theta H/L$, where H is the height of the microwire from the bottom end. The initial material line for $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation is as shown in Fig. 4b. The rotation of the material line with increasing surface strain is as shown in Fig. 5 and 6. The response of the micromorphic wire is also provided in Fig. 7 for comparison for a given internal length value. In the micromorphic approach, the penalty parameter H_χ is chosen sufficiently large such that γ_{cum} and γ_χ almost coincide. The chosen value of H_χ in the simulation is 10^4 MPa . The intrinsic length scale (ℓ) considered in the simulation is defined as $\ell = \sqrt{A/|H|}$ as proposed in (Ling et al., 2018), where H is the linear hardening modulus. H is estimated by performing a uniaxial tensile test on one element as proposed in (Ling, 2017). Its value is given by the ratio of τ^s divided by γ^s for one slip system at the beginning of its activation. Thus the estimated H value for $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation are 2500 MPa and 2000 MPa respectively. The intrinsic length scale can be varied by varying the constitutive parameter A . The various values of A and the intrinsic length scale to diameter ($\ell/2R$) ratio of microwire are given in the Table 2. The micromorphic response in Fig. 7 exhibits a linear hardening of the wire in contrast to the saturated classical crystal plasticity response. The magnitude of the slope depends on the value of the internal length as demonstrated in the following.

The effect of different $\ell/2R$ ratios on the size effects in torsion microwires has been studied for the two models considered in this work, namely the micromorphic and augmented Lagrangian SGP formulations. The torque vs surface strain curves of the micromorphic model is compared with the augmented Lagrangian SGP model. The cumulative plastic strain (γ_{cum}) fields for different $\ell/2R$ of microwire ($\ell/2R = 0.03, 0.07, 0.10$ and 0.44 for $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\ell/2R = 0.03, 0.08, 0.11$ and 0.50 for $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation) obtained using both models is as

Table 2: Numerical values of $\ell/2R$ ratio used in simulation

A (N)	0.1	0.5	1.0	10.0	20.0	30.0
$\ell/2R$ $\langle 001 \rangle$	0.03	0.07	0.10	0.31	0.44	0.54
$\ell/2R$ $\langle 111 \rangle$	0.03	0.08	0.11	0.35	0.50	0.61

shown in Fig. 8 and 9. It can be seen from Fig. 8 and 9 that, for low and intermediate values of the ratio $\ell/2R$, the two models predict the same accumulated plastic slip fields. In contrast, for the larger value $\ell/2R = 0.31$, the circumferential gradient has almost disappeared according to the augmented Lagrangian SGP model whereas it is still present in the micromorphic simulation. Increasing length scales for a fixed wire diameter leads to a strong decrease of the plastic strain gradient. This can be attributed to the fact that the energetic cost of plastic strain gradient increases with ℓ and the free energy of the sample is minimum for a limited value of the gradient. These observations are valid for both orientations $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$. Remarkably, the four-fold and six-fold patterns disappear for large enough internal length scale values.

The corresponding torque vs surface strain curves is provided in Fig. 10 and 11. They clearly show the size-dependent hardening effect for both models. For small and intermediate values of the internal length, the micromorphic and augmented Lagrangian SGP models are found to deliver the same overall responses. This result is expected since the value of the penalty parameter in the micromorphic model has been chosen to ensure such a correspondence. However, keeping the same value of the penalty parameter H_χ and increasing the internal length, or equivalently the value of the parameter A , leads to a saturation of the torque-shear strain curve for the micromorphic model. In contrast, the augmented Lagrangian SGP model predicts ever-increasing hardening. Fig. 10a and 11a show almost the same micromorphic response for $A = 20.0$ N and $A = 30.0$ N whereas distinct curves are obtained for the augmented Lagrangian SGP model, see Fig. 10b and 11b. This difference between the micromorphic and augmented Lagrangian SGP models has already been demonstrated analytically for the microcurl theory by Cordero et al. (2010) in the case of periodic shearing of a laminate at small strains and small rotations. The present new results show that this feature also exists at large strains for torsion. These observations apply to both orientations $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$. The strongest additional hardening effect is obtained when the internal length takes values comparable to the wire diameter, as expected.

7. Concluding remark

It is demonstrated that the CPFEM method is a powerful tool for a wide range of mechanical and materials science problems. The continuum framework of crystal plasticity allows solving diverse deformation mechanism for instance dislocation slip, twinning, and martensitic formation. The CPFEM with an appropriate homogenization method can able to deal with macroscopic material problems, for instance, the problems encountered

Fig. 5: Cumulative plastic strain (γ_{cum}) field in FCC single crystal for $\langle 001 \rangle$ crystal orientation in classical CP with respect to deformed configuration. The rotation of material line shown in Fig. 4b with increasing surface strain is shown by a black line on the cross-section

Fig. 6: Cumulative plastic strain (γ_{cum}) field in FCC single crystal for $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation in classical CP with respect to deformed configuration. The material line shown in Fig. 4b and it's rotation with increasing surface strain is shown by a black line on the cross-section

Fig. 7: Shear stress vs surface strain in FCC single crystal wires for $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation using classical crystal plasticity and micromorphic models.

in metal forming. The strength of the CPFEM lies in the fact that it can deal with complicated boundary conditions to predict the mechanical and microstructural material properties which are difficult to predict by experimental tests.

Another strength of the CPFEM is the extension to predict mechanical and microstructural properties which are not possible by the classical framework. The strain gradient crystal plasticity which is an extension of classical crystal plasticity framework can predict the experimentally observed size effects. The size effects are demonstrated for a single crystal torsion test using reduced-order strain gradient crystal plasticity. Another advantage of the CPFEM is that it can be used in conjunction with commercial or open-source FE solver as a user material subroutine.

Fig. 8: Cumulative plastic strain distribution in FCC single crystal wire cross-sections at different values of the $\ell/2R$ ratio for (a) micromorphic (b) augmented Lagrangian SGP model at surface strain of 0.08 (fields reported on the reference configuration).

Fig. 9: Cumulative plastic strain distribution in FCC single crystal for $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation at different values of $l/2R$ ratio for (a) micromorphic (b) augmented Lagrangian SGP model at surface strain of 0.08 (fields reported on the reference configuration)

Fig. 10: Normalized torque vs surface strain curves for FCC $\langle 001 \rangle$ crystal orientation for different values of A and equivalent $\ell/2R$ ratio using (a) micromorphic (b) augmented Lagrangian SGP model.

Fig. 11: Normalized torque vs surface strain curves for FCC $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystal orientation for different values of A and equivalent $\ell/2R$ ratio using (a) micromorphic (b) augmented Lagrangian SGP model.

References

- Abu Al-Rub, R., Voyiadjis, G., 2004. Determination of the material intrinsic length scale of gradient plasticity theory. *International Journal for Multiscale Computational Engineering* 2, 377–400.
- Acharya, A., Bassani, J., 2000. Lattice incompatibility and a gradient theory of crystal plasticity. *Acta Mater* 47, 11597 – 1611.
- Aifantis, E.C., 1984. On the microstructural origin of certain inelastic models. *Journal of Engineering Materials and technology* 106, 326–330.
- Aifantis, E.C., 1987. The physics of plastic deformation. *International Journal of Plasticity* 3, 211 – 247.
- Anand, L., Aslan, O., Chester, S.A., 2012. A large-deformation gradient theory for elastic–plastic materials: Strain softening and regularization of shear bands. *International Journal of Plasticity* 30-31, 116 – 143.
- Anand, L., Kothari, M., 1996. A computational procedure for rate-independent crystal plasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 44, 525 – 558.
- Asaro, R.J., 1983. Crystal Plasticity. *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 50, 921–934.
- Ashby, M.F., 1970. The deformation of plastically non-homogeneous materials. *The Philosophical Magazine: A Journal of Theoretical Experimental and Applied Physics* 21, 399–424.
- Aslan, O., Cordero, N., Gaubert, A., Forest, S., 2011. Micromorphic approach to single crystal plasticity and damage. *International Journal of Engineering Science* 49, 1311 – 1325.
- Bayerschen, E., 2016. Single-crystal gradient plasticity with an accumulated plastic slip: Theory and applications.
- Bayerschen, E., Stricker, M., Wulfinghoff, S., Weygand, D., Böhlke, T., 2015. Equivalent plastic strain gradient plasticity with grain boundary hardening and comparison to discrete dislocation dynamics. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 471.
- Bayley, C., Brekelmans, W., Geers, M., 2006. A comparison of dislocation induced back stress formulations in strain gradient crystal plasticity. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 43, 7268 – 7286. *Size-dependent Mechanics of Materials*.
- Busso, E.P., Cailletaud, G., 2005. On the selection of active slip systems in crystal plasticity. *International Journal of Plasticity* 21, 2212–2231.
- Cailletaud, G., Forest, S., Jeulin, D., Feyel, F., Galliet, I., Mounoury, V., Quilici, S., 2003. Some elements of microstructural mechanics. *Computational Materials Science* 27, 351 – 374.

- Casals, O., Očenášek, J., Alcalá, J., 2007. Crystal plasticity finite element simulations of pyramidal indentation in copper single crystals. *Acta Materialia* 55, 55 – 68.
- Chambon, R., Caillerie, D., Hassan, N.E., 1998. One-dimensional localisation studied with a second grade model. *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids* 17, 637 – 656.
- Cordero, N., Forest, S., Busso, E., Berbenni, S., Cherkaoui, M., 2012. Grain size effects on plastic strain and dislocation density tensor fields in metal polycrystals. *Computational Materials Science* 52, 7 – 13.
- Cordero, N., Gaubert, A., Forest, S., Busso, E.P., Gallerneau, F., Kruch, S., 2010. Size effects in generalised continuum crystal plasticity for two-phase laminates. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 58, 1963–1994.
- Delannay, L., 2018. Modeling of microscopic strain heterogeneity during wire drawing of pearlite. *Procedia Manufacturing* 15, 1893 – 1899. Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Metal Forming METAL FORMING 2018 September 16 – 19, 2018, Loisir Hotel Toyohashi, Toyohashi, Japan.
- Erdle, H., Böhlke, T., 2017. A gradient crystal plasticity theory for large deformations with a discontinuous accumulated plastic slip. *Computational Mechanics* 60, 923–942.
- Eringen, A., 1999. *Microcontinuum Field Theories*.
- Eringen, A., Suhubi, E., 1964. Nonlinear theory of simple micro-elastic solids—i. *International Journal of Engineering Science* 2, 189 – 203.
- Fleck, N., Hutchinson, J., 1993. A phenomenological theory for strain gradient effects in plasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 41, 1825 – 1857.
- Fleck, N., Hutchinson, J., 1997. Strain gradient plasticity. *Advances in Applied Mechanics* 33, 296–361.
- Fleck, N., Hutchinson, J., 2001. A reformulation of strain gradient plasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 49, 2245 – 2271.
- Fleck, N., Muller, G., Ashby, M., Hutchinson, J., 1994. Strain gradient plasticity: theory and experiment. *Acta Metallurgica et Materialia* 42, 475–487.
- Forest, S., 2005. Generalized continua, in: Buschow, K.J., Cahn, R.W., Flemings, M.C., Ilchner, B., Kramer, E.J., Mahajan, S., Veyssire, P. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Materials: Science and Technology*. Elsevier, Oxford, pp. 1 – 7.
- Forest, S., 2009. Micromorphic approach for gradient elasticity, viscoplasticity, and damage. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 135, 117–131.

- Forest, S., 2016. Nonlinear regularization operators as derived from the micromorphic approach to gradient elasticity, viscoplasticity and damage. *Proc. R. Soc. A* 472, 20150755.
- Forest, S., Lorentz, E., 2004 .
- Forest, S., Rubin, M., 2016. A rate-independent crystal plasticity model with a smooth elastic–plastic transition and no slip indeterminacy. *European Journal of Mechanics-A/Solids* 55, 278–288.
- Forest, S., Sedláček, R., 2000. Non-local plasticity at microscale: A dislocation based and cosserat model. *physica status solidi (b)* 221, 583 – 596.
- Fortin, M., Glowinski, R., 1983. Chapter iii on decomposition-coordination methods using an augmented lagrangian, in: *Studies in Mathematics and Its Applications*. Elsevier. volume 15, pp. 97–146.
- Gan, Z., He, Y., Liu, D., Zhang, B., Shen, L., 2014. Hall–petch effect and strain gradient effect in the torsion of thin gold wires. *Scripta Materialia* 87, 41 – 44.
- Gao, H., Huang, Y., 2001. Taylor-based nonlocal theory of plasticity. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 38, 2615 – 2637.
- Gao, H., Huang, Y., Nix, W., Hutchinson, J., 1999. Mechanism-based strain gradient plasticity— i. theory. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 47, 1239 – 1263.
- Greer, J.R., Oliver, W.C., Nix, W.D., 2005. Size dependence of mechanical properties of gold at the micron scale in the absence of strain gradients. *Acta Materialia* 53, 1821 – 1830.
- Guo, S., He, Y., Lei, J., Li, Z., Liu, D., 2017. Individual strain gradient effect on torsional strength of electropolished microscale copper wires. *Scripta Materialia* 130, 124 – 127.
- Gurtin, M.E., 2002. A gradient theory of single-crystal viscoplasticity that accounts for geometrically necessary dislocations. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 50, 5–32.
- Gurtin, M.E., Anand, L., 2005a. A theory of strain-gradient plasticity for isotropic, plastically irrotational materials. part i: Small deformations. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 53, 1624 – 1649.
- Gurtin, M.E., Anand, L., 2005b. A theory of strain-gradient plasticity for isotropic, plastically irrotational materials. part ii: Finite deformations. *International Journal of Plasticity* 21, 2297 – 2318.
- Haque, M., Saif, M., 2003. Strain gradient effect in nanoscale thin films. *Acta Materialia* 51, 3053 – 3061.
- Huang, Y., Gao, H., Nix, W., Hutchinson, J., 2000. Mechanism-based strain gradient plasticity—ii. analysis. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 48, 99 – 128.

- Jung, J.H., Na, Y., Cho, K.M., Dimiduk, D., Choi, Y., 2015. Microcompression behaviors of single crystals simulated by crystal plasticity finite element method. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A* 46.
- Kaiser, T., Menzel, A., 2019. An incompatibility tensor-based gradient plasticity formulation-Theory and numerics. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 345, 671 – 700.
- Kubin, L., Devincre, B., Hoc, T., 2008. Modeling dislocation storage rates and mean free paths in face-centered cubic crystals. *Acta materialia* 56, 6040–6049.
- Kuroda, M., Tvergaard, V., Ohashi, T., 2006. Simulations of micro-bending of thin foils using a scale dependent crystal plasticity model. *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering* 15, S13–S22.
- Lee, E.H., Liu, D.T., 1967. Finite strain elastic plastic theory with application to plane wave analysis. *Journal of Applied Physics* 38, 19–27.
- Li, S., Donohue, B.R., Kalidindi, S.R., 2008. A crystal plasticity finite element analysis of cross-grain deformation heterogeneity in equal channel angular extrusion and its implications for texture evolution. *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 480, 17 – 23.
- Ling, C., 2017. Modeling the intragranular ductile fracture of irradiated steels. effects of crystal anisotropy and strain gradient.
- Ling, C., Forest, S., Besson, J., Tanguy, B., Latourte, F., 2018. A reduced micromorphic single crystal plasticity model at finite deformations. application to strain localization and void growth in ductile metals. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 134, 43–69.
- Liu, D., He, Y., Dunstan, D.J., Zhang, B., Gan, Z., Hu, P., Ding, H., 2013. Toward a further understanding of size effects in the torsion of thin metal wires: An experimental and theoretical assessment. *International Journal of Plasticity* 41, 30 – 52.
- Liu, D., He, Y., Tang, X., Ding, H., Hu, P., Cao, P., 2012. Size effects in the torsion of microscale copper wires: Experiment and analysis. *Scripta Materialia* 66, 406 – 409.
- Liu, Y., Ngan, A., 2001. Depth dependence of hardness in copper single crystals measured by nanoindentation. *Scripta Materialia* 44, 237–241.
- Lubliner, J., Taylor, R., Auricchio, F., 1993. A new model of generalized plasticity and its numerical implementation. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 30, 3171 – 3184.
- Mayama, T., Noda, M., Chiba, R., Kuroda, M., 2011. Crystal plasticity analysis of texture development in magnesium alloy during extrusion. *International Journal of Plasticity* 27, 1916 – 1935. Special Issue In Honor of Nobutada Ohno.

- Miehe, C., Schröder, J., Schotte, J., 1999. Computational homogenization analysis in finite plasticity simulation of texture development in polycrystalline materials. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 171, 387 – 418.
- Mindlin, R., 1964. Micro-structure in linear elasticity 16, 51–78.
- Nakamachi, E., Xie, C., Harimoto, M., 2001. Drawability assessment of bcc steel sheet by using elastic/crystalline viscoplastic finite element analyses. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences* 43, 631 – 652.
- Needleman, A., 1988. Material rate dependence and mesh sensitivity in localization problems. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 67, 69 – 85.
- Niordson, C.F., 2008. Void growth to coalescence in a non-local material. *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids* 27, 222 – 233.
- Nix, W.D., Gao, H., 1998. Indentation size effects in crystalline materials: A law for strain gradient plasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 46, 411 – 425.
- Nouailhas, D., Cailletaud, G., 1995. Tension-torsion behavior of single-crystal superalloys: Experiment and finite element analysis. *International Journal of Plasticity* 11, 451 – 470.
- Očenášek, J., Ripoll, M.R., Weygand, S., Riedel, H., 2007. Multi-grain finite element model for studying the wire drawing process. *Computational Materials Science* 39, 23 – 28. *Proceedings of the 15th International Workshop on Computational Mechanics of Materials*.
- Peerlings, R., de Borst, R., Brekelmans, W., Geers, M., 2002. Localisation issues in local and nonlocal continuum approaches to fracture. *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids* 21, 175 – 189.
- Peerlings, R.H.J., De Borst, R., Brekelmans, W.A.M., De Vree, J.H.P., 1996. Gradient enhanced damage for quasi-brittle materials. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 39, 3391–3403.
- Qian, X., Zhang, S., Swaddiwudhipong, S., Shen, L., 2013. Temperature dependence of material length scale for strain gradient plasticity and its effect on near-tip opening displacement. *Fatigue I& Fracture of Engineering Materials I& Structures* 37.
- Raabe, D., Ma, D., Roters, F., 2007. Effects of initial orientation, sample geometry and friction on anisotropy and crystallographic orientation changes in single crystal microcompression deformation: A crystal plasticity finite element study. *Acta Materialia* 55, 4567 – 4583.
- Roters, F., Eisenlohr, P., Hantcherli, L., Tjahjanto, D., Bieler, T., Raabe, D., 2010. Overview of constitutive laws, kinematics, homogenization and multiscale methods in crystal plasticity finite-element modeling: Theory, experiments, applications. *Acta Materialia* 58, 1152 – 1211.

- Ryś, M., Forest, S., Petryk, H., 2020. A micromorphic crystal plasticity model with the gradient-enhanced incremental hardening law. *International Journal of Plasticity* 128, 102655.
- Scherer, J., Besson, J., Forest, S., Hure, J., Tanguy, B., 2019. Strain gradient crystal plasticity with evolving length scale: Application to voided irradiated materials. *European Journal of Mechanics-A/Solids* 77, 103768.
- Shu, J.Y., Fleck, N.A., 1999. Strain gradient crystal plasticity: size-dependent deformation of bicrystals. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 47, 297 – 324.
- Staroselsky, A., Cassenti, B.N., 2011. Creep, plasticity, and fatigue of single crystal superalloy. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 48, 2060 – 2075.
- Stölken, J., Evans, A., 1998. A microbend test method for measuring the plasticity length scale. *Acta Materialia* 46, 5109 – 5115.
- Toupin, R.A., 1962. Elastic materials with couple-stresses. *Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis* 11, 385–414.
- Uchic, M., Dimiduk, D., Florando, J., Nix, W., 2004. Sample dimensions influence strength and crystal plasticity. *Science (New York, N.Y.)* 305, 986–9.
- Vignjevic, R., Djordjevic, N., Vuyst, T.D., Gemkow, S., 2018. Modelling of strain softening materials based on equivalent damage force. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 335, 52 – 68.
- Voyiadjis, G.Z., Al-Rub, R.K.A., 2005. Gradient plasticity theory with a variable length scale parameter. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 42, 3998 – 4029.
- Wang, Y., Raabe, D., Klüber, C., Roters, F., 2004. Orientation dependence of nanoindentation pile-up patterns and of nanoindentation microtextures in copper single crystals. *Acta Materialia* 52, 2229 – 2238.
- Weimin, Z., Shiwen, W., Balint, D., Lin, J., 2011. Crystal plasticity finite element process modeling for hydro-forming micro-tubular components. *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering* 24, 78.
- Wulfinghoff, S., Bayerschen, E., Böhlke, T., 2013. A gradient plasticity grain boundary yield theory. *International Journal of Plasticity* 51, 33–46.
- Wulfinghoff, S., Böhlke, T., 2012. Equivalent plastic strain gradient enhancement of single crystal plasticity: theory and numerics. *Proc. R. Soc. A* 468, 2682–2703.
- Xie, C., Nakamachi, E., 2002. Investigations of the formability of bcc steel sheets by using crystalline plasticity finite element analysis. *Materials and Design* 23, 59 – 68.

- Zaafarani, N., Raabe, D., Singh, R., Roters, F., Zaeferrer, S., 2006. Three-dimensional investigation of the texture and microstructure below a nanoindent in a cu single crystal using 3d ebsd and crystal plasticity finite element simulations. *Acta Materialia* 54, 1863 – 1876.
- Zbib, H.M., Aifantis, E.C., 1988. On the structure and width of shear bands. *Scripta Metallurgica* 22, 703–708.
- ming Zhang, H., huai Dong, X., Wang, Q., zong Li, H., 2013. Micro-bending of metallic crystalline foils by non-local dislocation density based crystal plasticity finite element model. *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China* 23, 3362 – 3371.
- Zhang, Y., Lorentz, E., Besson, J., 2018. Ductile damage modelling with locking-free regularised gtn model. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 113, 1871–1903.
- Zhuang, W., Wang, S., Cao, J., Lin, J., Hartl, C., 2010. Modelling of localised thinning features in the hydroforming of micro-tubes using the crystal-plasticity fe method. *Adv Manuf Technol* 47, 859–865.